

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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EVALUATION THE EFFICIENCY OF SUNLIGHT THERAPY AS AN INTERVENTION
FOR PATIENTS IN A SKILLED NURSING FACILITY TO HELP IMPROVE DEPRESSION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTORAL OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The World Health Organization has identified major depressive disorder as the leading form of mental health disability worldwide (Oldham & Ciraulo, 2014). Community-dwelling older adults (OA) have a range of 8% to 16% who report depressive symptoms (Blazer, 2003). Within nursing homes, the prevalence of symptoms of depression ranges anywhere from 35% to 48.7% (Blaze, 2003; Santiago & Mattos, 2014). OAs diagnosed with depression are more susceptible to poor health outcomes such as diabetes, congestive heart failure, failure to thrive, vitamin D deficiency, arthritis, kidney disease, ulcers, Alzheimer's disease, and stroke (Baggerly et al. 2015; Blazer, 2003; Gonul & Durmanz, 2017; Oldham & Ciraulo, 2014; Sumaya et al., 2001). To address this issue, the researcher is proposing the use of sunlight therapy as an intervention. The purpose of this DNP Project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a sunlight intervention for OAs suffering from depression who reside in a nursing facility. Although, due to COVID-19 this project is on hold. This programmatic evaluation and review of literature shows a significant opportunity to improve depressive symptoms of OAs residing in skilled nursing homes during and after this current crisis.

Keywords: depression, sunlight therapy, skilled nursing home older adults, seasonal affective disorder, IOWA Model.

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Background

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified major depressive disorder (MDD) as the leading form of mental health disability worldwide (Oldham & Ciraulo, 2014).

Community-dwelling older adults (OA) have a range of 8% to 16% who report depressive symptoms (Blazer, 2003). Within nursing homes, the prevalence of symptoms of depression range anywhere from 35% to 48.7% (Blaze, 2003; Santiago & Mattos, 2014). Older adults in nursing facilities are in transition from being independent to being dependent, often experiencing a loss of friends or family (Sumaya et al., 2001). Many nursing home residents are confined due to global physical decline and immobility (Sumaya et al., 2001). There is a correlation between sunlight and depression, according to the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders IV (DSM-5)*, which is referred to as Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD). The incidence of SAD varies with the seasons and the amount of sunlight per day, typically starting in the late fall and early winter and going away during the spring and summer.

There is a biological response when an individual is exposed to sunlight. Sunlight stimulates the hypothalamus to release corticotropin-releasing hormone into the pituitary gland, which controls the circadian rhythm and regulates these hormones. Circadian rhythm is the body's internal clock, which stimulates the sleep-wake cycle (Perera et al., 2016). Lack of sunlight has shown to dysregulate the circadian rhythm, leading to poor sleeping patterns, obesity, depression, and heart disease (Perera et al., 2016; Varghese & Brown, 2001). Older adults diagnosed with depression are more susceptible to poor health outcomes such as diabetes, congestive heart failure, failure to thrive, vitamin D deficiency, arthritis, kidney disease, ulcers, Alzheimer's disease, and stroke (Baggerly et al. 2015; Blazer, 2003; Gonul & Durmanz, 2017; Oldham & Ciraulo, 2014; Sumaya et al., 2001). In addition, 20% of OAs who experience

medical comorbidities or suffer from a health crisis are more likely to die within the first four months if they suffer from depression (Blazer, 2003). Health care spending on depression among OAs has doubled in the past 10 years (Blazer, 2003; Oldham & Ciraulo, 2014; Sumaya et al., 2001). By 2050, the population aged 65 and older is projected to be 83.7 million, almost double the estimated population in 2012, which was 43.1 million. Baby Boomers, who began turning 65 in 2011, account for this increase in OAs (Ortman et al., 2014). This suggests that the numbers of older individuals suffering from depression will also increase.

Research suggests sunlight therapy is an effective treatment for depression in OAs residing in nursing homes (Baggerly et al., 2015; Chang, 2017; Durvasula et al., 2015; Holick, 2011; Perera et al., 2016; Sumaya et al., 2001; Xue et al., 2017). However, there are no guidelines for using sunlight as an evidence-based method for treating symptoms of depression among OAs within nursing facilities. There is evidence recommending the amount of sunlight exposure needed, yet many facilities do not utilize it in their current practices.

Significance

It is critical to develop evidence-based practice guidelines to increase the efficacy of the use of sunlight therapy with OAs residing in nursing facilities to reduce depressive symptoms. Adoption of guidelines for the use of sunlight could have a profound impact on depressive symptoms, as well as other comorbidities. Also, this intervention may decrease the necessity for antidepressant medications, and reduce the effects associated with or the incidence of polypharmacy. In the facility in which this project is planned, OAs have limited exposure to natural sunlight due to immobility, fall risk, and physical decline (Sumaya et al., 2001). The limited sun exposure may contribute to patients feeling lethargic, poorly motivated, confused,

and/or sad, in addition to having insomnia (Simning & Simons, 2017; Sumaya et al., 2001; Zhao, Ma, Wu, Chi, & Bai, 2018).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP Project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a sunlight intervention for older adults (OAs) suffering from depression, who reside in a nursing facility. The project sought to determine whether levels of depression among OAs would decrease by using sunlight therapy provided five days per week for a duration of five weeks.

Theoretical Framework: Iowa Model

The framework selected for this project was the Iowa Model, due to its ability to guide the development of an intervention to address depression among OAs living in a skilled nursing facility. A framework offers a guide for investigators to implement projects and interpret their findings. The Iowa Model was developed 25 years ago by a team from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (UIHC) College of Nursing (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Hanrahan, 2019). The Iowa Model has been extensively used in healthcare projects to assist providers in implementing and evaluating evidence-based practices to address problems (Buckwalter et al., 2017). It has been used across the world (in 50 states and 130 countries) for clinical projects in health care, as well as in nursing education and administration (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

The model was revised by the Iowa Model Collaborative in 2017. The revision decreased the number of stages and added additional quality control measures. The Iowa Model can be broken down into a five-step process. The first step is identifying the topic of interest by determining the trigger for the problem. In selecting a topic, the researcher should explore the literature and evidence on current practices. There are two questions to be asked: Is there an

identifiable problem within the organization? And, how did the trigger come to be identified and is it relevant or a priority that needs to be addressed?

The second step is identifying the team members who can contribute to the development and implementation of the project. Stakeholders should also be engaged in the project, as they can contribute relevant information regarding organizational policies and systems that can facilitate or impede implementation of the project. Engaging the team and leaders within the organization can assist in decision-making due to their level of expertise with the project.

The third step is conducting a review of the literature to gather existing research on the topic. The literature is critically appraised based upon its feasibility, effectiveness, and appropriateness to the topic of interest (Doody & Doody, 2011). The literature should be explored extensively, reaching saturation (Polit & Beck, 2019). The project should add to the depth of knowledge within the field to improve current practices.

Once the literature has been adequately identified, appraised, and synthesized, the fourth step is to create a project design for practice change. Within this step, the researcher must identify how to engage the team and create a detailed, multi-step process that will ensure the change will take place. This step will set the standard for the practice guideline, assessment, actions, and treatment required for the change to occur (Doody & Doody, 2011). In creating an evidence-based practice guideline, the steps of the Iowa Model will assist in determining the effectiveness of the practice change (Doody & Doody, 2011). In the creation of this pilot project, it is critical to assess sustainability, as well as to consider the individual patient's needs while implementing the intervention.

The fifth step, dissemination, is the implementation of the project in other areas of an organization. The process of dissemination should be outlined to ensure that the project is

replicated and sustained (Buckwalter et al., 2017). This step should focus on the organization's strengths and perceived benefits of the practice change, including communication with all the team members so they are all aware of the project outcome and implementation (Doody & Doody, 2011). This step also includes identification of barriers and how to use the organization's strengths to mitigate them. Once the pilot is disseminated, steps should be taken to ensure its sustainability, which can be accomplished by changing policies, procedures, and guidelines. There should be ongoing monitoring and training at targeted points to ensure the practice change is continuing as intended (Doody & Doody, 2011).

Application of the Iowa Model to the Project

The Iowa Model begins with identifying the trigger (see Figure 1). The trigger in this project was the high number of OAs diagnosed with depression within a nursing facility. The first step was to identify the topic. In this project, the author selected light therapy due to her professional experience working in a skilled nursing facility with OAs suffering from depression and being treated with antidepressants. Many OAs residing in the nursing facility have limited access to sunlight, which can exacerbate their depressive symptoms and co-occurring disorders.

Figure 1

Iowa Model Revised

The priorities of the pilot project were to reduce symptoms related to depression. In doing so, it was hoped that the costs related to comorbidities would decrease. The cost of major depression is growing and directly correlates to the risk for comorbidities (Blaze 2003; Perera et al., 2016). The pilot project was going to take place at a semi-locked facility, with 80% of the population suffering from a mental disorder. There has been an increasing number of residents diagnosed with or continuing to have exacerbations of depression.

In order to address this issue, the researcher proposed the use of sunlight therapy as an intervention because of its low-cost and non-invasive nature. Sunlight therapy is a non-pharmacological intervention that has shown efficacy in the treatment of depression but needs further investigation within the OA population (Blazer, 2003; Gonul & Durmanz, 2017; Oldham & Ciraulo, 2014, Sumaya et al., 2001). When reviewing the project with the team, which was composed of psychiatrists, nurses, social workers, and psychologists, the clinicians believed it was imperative to try natural sunlight in addition to their regular regime of treatment for the patients' depression.

Purpose and Formulation of Team

The second step of the pilot project was to use sunlight therapy to help OAs residing in the nursing home to decrease feelings of depression. The team consisted of a nursing assistant, licensed vocational nurses, the assistant director of nursing, and the director of the nursing facility. The director and senior marketing representative for the facility were to be notified of the results at the end of the pilot project. There would be weekly meetings with the team and stakeholders (Administer and Director of Nursing [DON]) to keep them updated on the project. This would ensure the collaboration of all team members and stakeholders during the initiation and implementation of the pilot project.

Relevant and Related Research

The third step is the gathering of relevant and related research. The World Health Organization World Mental Health Survey Initiative, conducted from 2005 to 2019, found that the incidence of major depression among adults rose from 13.8 million to 15.4 million in the United States (Greenberg et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2016). Among OAs, depression is associated with other healthcare problems, such as an increased risk of developing diabetes, arthritis, kidney disease, ulcers, strokes, and failure to thrive as they continue to age (Blaze, 2003). The Harvard School of Public Health stipulated that depression is anticipated to be the second global leading cause of disability by 2020, trailing only to heart disease (Perera et al., 2016).

The typical method of treatment for OAs with depression is to prescribe antidepressants, which occurs most frequently with women (Charlesworth et al., 2015). Recent studies have shown that the proportion of OA women suffering from depression has risen from 3.2% to 16.5% in the United States (Charlesworth et al., 2015). There is evidence to demonstrate that as the population ages, depression will be the second leading cause of disability, requiring the creation of a low-cost, safe, and easily accessible intervention. This is a crucial issue for the OA population in the U.S., as many are living longer and requiring skilled care. It was hoped that sunlight therapy can provide a safe and easy to administer intervention to address depressive symptoms.

Practice Change Pilot

The fourth step is implementation of the project. This pilot would consist of 10 participants who received sunlight therapy. All participants must have had a pre-existing diagnosis of depression, as defined by the DSM-5. Each participant would complete two depression screening tools, the Geriatric Depression Scale and Patient Health Questionnaire

(PHQ9) (Durmaz, Soysal, Ellidokuz, & Isik, 2018; Yesavage et al., 1982-1983). The screening tools would be used to measure the participants' level of depression prior to beginning the sunlight therapy and after completing five weeks of sunlight therapy. The sunlight therapy would be provided five days a week, for 30 minutes a day, and for a duration of five weeks (Baggerly et al., 2015; Durvasula et al., 2015, Holick, 2011; Sumaya et al., 2001). The participants would be reassessed at the end of the intervention, using both screening tools.

Adoption of Practice

After the implementation of the pilot project, the data will be evaluated to determine if sunlight therapy was effective and supports the current literature. This step will be the dissemination of sunlight therapy into practice and a determination of how this intervention could be utilized in different care settings. If the pilot project proves successful, the intervention would be implemented throughout the facility. This will be accomplished by speaking with stakeholders and developing a policy related to the guideline, which outlines the procedures for implementation of sunlight therapy.

Review of Literature

A review of literature was conducted to identify studies related to the efficacy of sunlight therapy as an intervention for depression among OAs residing in nursing facilities. This literature review was conducted utilizing the following databases: PubMed, CINAHL, and EBSCO. Search terms included “sunlight therapy in older adults,” “depression in nursing facilities,” and “sunlight therapy for treatment of depression in older adults.” The search limitations used were journals published from 1999 to 2020, and in English only. The literature review is divided into the following sections: pathophysiology and diagnosis, seasonal affective disorder, sunlight and light therapy, other therapies, and Iowa Model and Guideline Implementation.

Pathophysiology and Diagnosis

Depression is a disease that is linked to abnormalities in the function of the subcortical limbic system. In patients who are depressed, several monoamine neurotransmitters interact and cause changes in mood. The three monoamines that will be described in this review are dopamine, norepinephrine (NE) and serotonin (5HT). These neurotransmitters are released consistently within the brain to regulate mood. When there is a dysregulation of these neurotransmitters, depression can develop (Hassler, 2010). Depression has been hypothesized as a monoamine-deficiency. The location in the brain where dopamine, NE and 5HT interact is within the midbrain, which houses the hypothalamus, and brainstem nuclei, which regulate sleep (Hassler, 2010; Ressler & Nemeroff, 2000). These neurotransmitters interact in the regulation of a broad range of brain functions, such as mood, attention, reward processing, sleep, appetite, and cognition (Hassler, 2010; Ressler & Nemeroff, 2000). Dysregulation can be brought on by multiple factors, such as loss, stress, lack of independence, financial insecurity, feeling alone/being far from family, and lack of socialization. In the OA population residing in nursing

homes, these factors correlate with a high prevalence of depression (Blazer, 2003; Gonul & Durmanz, 2017; Sumaya et al., 2001).

According to the DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2013), for a diagnosis of depression, a patient must present with five or more symptoms over a two-week period. This diagnosis includes depressed mood or anhedonia. There are also secondary symptoms of depression, which are appetite or weight changes, sleep difficulties, psychomotor agitation or retardation, fatigue or loss of energy, diminished ability to think or concentrate, feelings of worthlessness or excessive guilt, and suicidality (Tolentino & Schmidt, 2018). Depression is common among OAs residing in nursing homes, which makes it a public health problem. It is often associated with non-modifiable risk factors, such as chronic disease, cognitive dysfunction, and functional impairment. Older adults living in nursing homes have added risk factors due to economic struggles or relocation (Tolentino & Schmidt, 2018). Thus, it is important to address the modifiable risk factors related to depression, such as social isolation, limited outdoor activities, and cognitive stimulation. Sunlight can be a non-pharmacological intervention that can benefit OAs who are depressed, living in skilled nursing facilities and addressing the risk factors.

Seasonal Affective Disorder

For this section, the electronic databases of PubMed and Google Scholar were reviewed for publications on pathophysiology and publications relevant to the physiology of sunlight and the effects of sunlight. Key terms utilized included “pathophysiology,” “sunlight therapy,” and “depression.” Reference lists of the selected articles were searched for additional relevant articles.

When the brain does not receive enough sunlight, it can produce too much of the sleep hormone (melatonin), which causes impairment of the hypothalamic suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN). The SCN plays a central role in regulating the hormonal oscillations of the circadian rhythm (Gillette & Tischkua, 1999). This dysregulation produces too much melatonin and too little of the hormone serotonin, which then disrupts the circadian rhythm, leading to sleep deprivation (Lieverse et al., 2011). This also affects the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis (HPA axis) (Baggerly et al., 2015; Durvasula et al., 2015; Holick, 2011; Sumaya et al., 2001). The HPA axis is the area of the brain in which the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, and adrenal gland all communicate to release the hormones cortisol and dexamethasone.

When there is a dysregulation related to a lack of sunlight, the communication system between the glands and the hypothalamus is disrupted. This leads to excess cortisol production and the suppression of dexamethasone (Varghese & Brown, 2001). Light therapy influences these depression-associated neurotransmitter systems and targets the same brain structures as antidepressant drug treatments. Sunlight activates the SCN, which supports the regulation of the circadian pacemaker in the brain (Lieverse et al., 2011). A meta-analysis of more than 70 clinical trials identified light therapy as an acceptable option for OAs with seasonal affective disorder (SAD). In addition, several studies have shown an overall benefit of light therapy for individuals with non-seasonal depression of all ages (Chang et al., 2017; Xue et al., 2017). Three meta-analyses (Chang et al., 2017; Perera et al., 2016; Xue et al., 2017) have validated the use of light therapy for OAs experiencing seasonal affective disorder.

Sunlight and Light Therapy

For this section, the review of literature was conducted through PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. Search terms included “sunlight therapy,” “depression,” and “OA.” Key terms

included “pathophysiology,” “sunlight therapy,” and “depression.” Light therapy has been identified as an efficacious alternative treatment for depression (Baggerly et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2017; Durvasula et al., 2015; Holick, 2011; Sumaya., et al., 2001; Xue et al. 2017). Light therapy functions in the same manner as sunlight. When an individual is exposed to sunlight, it stimulates the hypothalamus to release corticotropin-releasing hormone into the pituitary gland, which then controls the circadian rhythm, regulating these hormones. Circadian rhythm is the body's internal clock, which stimulates the sleep-wake cycle (Perera et al., 2016). Research shows that sunlight exposure can help to improve the mental health status of OAs. The amount of sunlight an individual should be exposed to per day is approximately 600 International Units, or approximately 30 minutes (Baggerly et al., 2015; Durvasula et al., 2015; Holick, 2011; Sumaya et al., 2001). When OAs are exposed to sunlight on a regular basis, their symptoms of depression improve (Baggerly et al., 2015; Durvasula et al. 2015; Holick, 2011; Sumaya et al., 2001).

Other Therapies to Treat Depression

Psychotherapy and antidepressants are the main forms of treatment for depression among OAs (Chang et al., 2018; Siming & Simons, 2017; Sumaya et al., 2001; Zhao et al., 2018). However, the use of psychotherapy to treat depression is limited due to the number of therapists available in the nursing facility community (Siming & Simons, 2017). This means that antidepressants are the most common form of treatment (Chang et al., 2018; Fredrick et al., 2007). However, research indicates that antidepressants are not as effective for treating OAs because 10 to 20% of patients will progress to chronic or major depression despite treatment (Zhao et al. 2018). Also, OAs who use antidepressants are at greater risk of developing side effects, such as QT prolongation, weight changes, nausea, vomiting, dizziness, constipation,

headache, insomnia, agitation, and overall exacerbation of their depressive symptoms. In addition, approximately 8% of OAs who start taking SSRIs will develop hyponatremia, which may lead to seizures and confusion or trigger Syndrome of Inappropriate Antidiuretic Hormone (SIADH) (Chang et al., 2018; Frank, 2014; Taylor, 2015; Weiss, 2011; Zhao et al., 2018). These side effects can have significant health consequences for OAs, given their co-morbidities and overall general health issues.

Iowa Model and Project Implementation

A review was conducted utilizing PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar to review the literature regarding the use of the Iowa Model and adopting new evidence-based practices and clinical guidelines. The search terms included “Iowa Model,” “guideline implementation,” “implementation,” and “barriers.” The limits of this search were English-language articles that were published 2011 to 2015.

Implementation of a practice change can be a complex process, involving multiple steps and stakeholders. The Iowa Model (Buckwalter et al., 2017, Doody & Doody, 2011; Hanrahan, 2019) has been used to guide clinical practices across a variety of settings and populations. Because sunlight therapy for OAs in nursing facilities is a new practice, an established model can guide the process through the stages of development, implementation, and sustainment. There is no practice guideline for incorporating sunlight therapy into the daily schedule at nursing facilities. Therefore, further assessment is needed to determine the effectiveness of sunlight therapy in lifting patients’ moods, to make it a daily practice.

A similar project was conducted by Sumaya et al. (2001), in which bright light therapy was used to decrease depression in institutionalized OAs. This research tested the hypothesis that chronic light deprivation may be responsible for some depressive symptoms. The aim of the

study was to investigate the effects of light therapy as a treatment modality for depression among institutionalized OAs. The results showed that the treatment was effective for 66% of the participants in the study. The researchers found that depression was greater among OAs who had been institutionalized for the longest period. In a meta-analysis of light therapy for OAs with non-seasonal depression, light therapy was an effective treatment. Moreover, the review indicated that there were no severe side effects suffered by the light treatment group, as compared to the placebo group (Zhao et al., 2018). This result suggests that light therapy is a viable intervention for the treatment of depression among OAs who live in a skilled nursing facility.

Summary

This review of literature highlights how sunlight therapy can be used as an adjunct therapy for OAs suffering from depression. In the systematic review published by Zhao et al. (2018), the researchers found light therapy to be an effective form of treatment in depressed OAs. The review also concluded that there were no severe side effects between the light treatment and a placebo group. The evidence reviewed supports incorporating a sunlight therapy treatment modality for OAs suffering from depression in nursing facilities, as it could decrease symptoms of depression and polypharmacy.

Methods

The purpose of this DNP project was to evaluate the use of sunlight therapy for OAs suffering from depression and facilitate the adoption of an evidence-based guideline to integrate the practice into the facility. Due to many unforeseen circumstances, this program evaluation study was not able to be carried out at this time. Accordingly, this section will provide a discussion of how the project's design, timeline, setting, measures, ethical limitations, and data analysis would have been conducted.

Design

The project will use an EBP approach employing the Iowa Model to determine the effectiveness of using sunlight therapy as an adjunct to regular treatment for depression.

Setting

The project will take place at a SNF, in Orange County, California. The SNF has 143 beds and is a semi-locked facility with 80% of the residents diagnosed with a mental illness. The facility has approximately 167 nurses and 40 contracted providers. The project team consisted of the project author, the DNP project chair, the facility's director of nursing and the nursing assistants.

Participants

The residents will be selected based upon their ability to fully participate in the project and have a PHQ-9 score of five and above. The PHQ-9 is administered to all residents during their initial intake into the facility. First, the Director of Nursing (DON) will review patient charts to identify all patients who received a score of five or higher on the PHQ-9. A score of five was selected since this would indicate that the patient had at least a mild form of depression. Patients will be included in the project if they are taking an antidepressant medication, are

cognitively intact, over 50 years of age, have a diagnosis of depression, and are not taking medications which cause photosensitivity. Patients with a score less than five on the PHQ-9 or have a medical diagnosis, which makes them sensitive to sun exposure will be excluded. These residents will be provided a flier, which contains information regarding the project. The flier will contain contact information should they wish to participate in the project (see Appendix B). Once the residents contact the project author, they will be provided an informational cover letter (See Appendix C), which will present information about the project. After receiving the informational cover letter, the residents can begin their participation in the project. It is anticipated that 15 residents will agree to participate in the project. Residents can discontinue their participation at any time.

Procedures

An in-service will be provided by the project author to the nursing staff that will be involved in taking the residents outside. They will be provided an explanation of the project's purpose as well as their role in aiding in charting sun therapy time. The nursing staff will also be informed of the benefits of sun exposure to obtain buy in. Their importance to the project will be explained, since they are vital members of the team who will be responsible for ensuring the residents are exposed to the sun at the designated time.

Pilot project steps:

1. Residents will be provided with an informational flyer regarding the project.
2. The project author will consult with bedside staff with regards to the health and mental status of the residents who were selected.
3. The project author will then speak with selected residents to determine their interest in participating in the pilot project.

4. The project will be explained and residents willing to participate will be given an informational cover letter.
5. The first day of the pilot project, participants will be given the PHQ-9 screening tool again, along with the GDS. The project author will administer the surveys one-to-one to allow for questions to be addressed.
6. Once the surveys have been completed, the following day the nursing staff will begin taking the residents outside to be exposed to sunlight. This will occur 30 minutes a day, five days a week for five weeks. The residents will be exposed to sunlight between the hours of 9:00 AM to 11:00 AM, depending on the weather.
7. The nursing staff will be provided a timer, so they are able to track the 30 minutes that the patient is taken outside. This will decrease the possibility of the resident staying outside too long. The timer will buzz when it is time to bring the resident inside.
8. Every week the author will audit data collected and examine it to ensure residents are participating in the pilot project. After completion of the five weeks of sunlight therapy, the ten to fifteen residents will complete the PHQ-9 and GDS to determine if there was a decrease in their level of depression.

Instruments

Participant demographic data (e.g., self-reported age, race, ethnicity, marital status, level of education and years in the facility) will also be collected on an author-generated tool. The project will utilize two depression screening tools called the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) and the Geriatric Depression Screening (GDS). The PHQ-9 is a tool currently used in the project facility to screen for depression.

Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9)

The PHQ-9 is a commonly used depression screening tool (see Appendix D). It is a nine-item tool to assess depressive disorders and is administered by the project facility as part of the intake process. It uses a four-point Likert scale with a zero being “not at all,” a one is “several days,” two indicates “more than half the days,” and three being “nearly every day.” The items on the PHQ -9 align with the DSM-5 diagnostic criteria of anhedonia, depressed mood, trouble sleeping, feeling tired, change in appetite, guilt or worthlessness, trouble concentrating, feeling slowed down or restless, and suicidal thoughts. The residents are asked how often, over the last two weeks, they have been bothered by any of the previously mentioned depressive symptoms. Scores on the PHQ-9 can range from 0-27, with scores of ≥ 5 , ≥ 10 , ≥ 15 , representing mild, moderate and severe levels of depression, respectively (Gilbody, et al., 2007; Kroenke et al., 2001; Mitchell et al., 2009; Wittkamp et al., 2007).

Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS): Short Form

The GDS short form is a 15-item scale designed specifically to measure depression in the elderly (see Appendix E). The short form has 15 items and was developed to address challenges associated with assessing the elderly. The responses to the items are “yes” (1) or “no” (0). The scores range from zero to 15 with 0 to 4 indicating no depression, 5 to 8 mild depression, 9 to 11 moderate depression, and 12 to 15 severe depression (Herrmann et al., 1996). The validity of this screening tool among community-dwelling older adults was found to have a 75%-84% sensitivity rate and a 77%-95% specificity rate (Wancata et al., 2006; Yesavage et al., 1983.) The GDS has a test-retest reliability of 0.68 to 0.94 (Parmelee et al. 1989; Pedraza et al. 2009).

Ethical Considerations

This project was submitted to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Los Angeles. The project facility has granted permission to conduct the project (see Appendix A for letter of project approval). There is limited risk to the residents, since their sun exposure will be only 30 minutes. The time scheduled for sun exposure would not interfere with other therapies the resident may need to attend.

Residents will be de-identified using a random number that will be assigned to them in order to track their progress and completion of surveys for the project. Data will be collected and maintained on an Excel spreadsheet and kept in a password protected computer to which only the project author will have access. The data will be analyzed in aggregate to ensure anonymity of the resident.

Results

Data will be analyzed to identify the mean percentage on the pre- and posttest for the PHQ-9 (See Table 1) and GDS (see Table 2). Baseline characteristics will be established by pre-intervention scores. Residents will be grouped into mild, moderate and severe depression per their PHQ-9 scores.

Table 1

PHQ-9 Scores

Residents	Pre-intervention scores	Post-intervention scores	Score Difference
456	TBD	TBD	TBD
789			
987			
654			
123			
321			
147			
741			
258			
852			
	Mean %	Mean %	

Table 2*GDS Scores*

Residents	Pre-intervention scores	Post-intervention scores	Difference
456	TBD	TBD	TBD
789			
987			
654			
123			
321			
147			
741			
258			
852			
	Mean %	Mean %	

A Cronbach's alpha on the PHQ-9 and GDS scores for the pre- and posttest will be compared with reported levels when obtained.

Timeline

To ensure access to sunlight this project was going to begin in July 2020, and end by August 2020. Permission was granted to conduct the project; however, due to the COVID pandemic the project was halted (see Appendix A). The timeline is outlined in Table 3.

Table 3*Timeline*

May	June	July	August	September	October	November
Submit to IRB		Handing out fliers. Interview residents, conduct pretest (PHQ-9 & GDS), in-service with staff. Start intervention	Follow up bi-weekly for data	Complete Posttest PHQ-9 & GDS screening	Analyze data & evaluation of intervention Meet with team lead for data analysis	If data shows decrease signs of depression. Construct guideline

Evaluation

Due to the pandemic, this project was put on hold. However, the research shows that sunlight therapy is an effective treatment for symptoms related to depression. In this pilot project, the difference in scores on the GDS and PHQ-9 would be calculated and displayed in a bar graph to show the pre- and posttest comparison scores. A change between the pre- and posttest scores would be calculated for each patient to determine if there was an improvement in their level of depression. In this project change would be represented on a bar graph.

Discussion

Due to the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, this project was put on hold due to social distancing requirements and the risks to the vulnerable population which the project was targeting. In addition, the project facility had many devastating losses due to the pandemic and was no longer able to accommodate the project. During the pandemic, over the course of the year, more than 70 residents were diagnosed with COVID-19 and 15 residents lost their lives. This shut down the facility to only essential staff. All psychiatric services and other services were conducting patient visits through telemedicine and, thus, providing sunlight therapy was not possible. Many of the patients were quarantined due to exposure or diagnosis of COVID-19, which also led to this project to be placed on hold. There was a high turnover rate among administration and staff. All these factors required that the pilot project be changed to a programmatic evaluation and literature review to provide evidence-based practice recommendations in treating OAs suffering from depression in skilled nursing homes. Significant information was identified through the review of literature that demonstrated the importance of sunlight therapy.

The collection of data in relation to the PHQ-9 and GDS was consistent with current research. The current research showed that sunlight therapy improves symptoms of depression. A systematic review and meta-analysis by Change et al. (2018) which included eight trials and 395 participants, showed that there was an improvement in depression when patients were given sunlight therapy. In the studies, the GDS was used in five trials and showed larger effects than those studies using other depression scales. The results were that depression severity significantly decreased after light therapy. Additionally, eight trials used the GDS as a primary measure for depression and found a significant effect size of 0.574, favoring light therapy. The

PHQ-9 was used in a pilot study using light therapy for 30 minutes a day for 14 days, which showed a mean improvement in depressed mood 0.46 (Leggett, et al. 2018). This DNP pilot project would have also demonstrated that there was a correlation between sunlight therapy and depression scores on the PHQ-9 and GDS.

Limitations

This project had several limitations. The most significant limitation was due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This facility, along with many others nursing homes, experienced unforeseen and devastating losses. Over the year more than half of their residents were diagnosed or had to be placed on strict quarantine due to contact with others who had COVID-19. Many services had to be placed on hold, some terminated, and many others had to be done via telemedicine. There was an increase in turnover for all levels of staffing. The only ones allowed in the facility were essential staff. Due to this, the Administer and Director of Nursing contacted and informed the author that due to all these unforeseen events this project could not be conducted at this time.

Another limitation at the beginning of this project was obtaining support from a facility willing to implement sunlight therapy. There was lack of support from organizations due to their reluctance in identifying patients who were depressed. Another limitation was staff availability for providing and monitoring the patients who were going to receive sunlight therapy. This would have been addressed by having staffing and leadership involved in creating a time during every shift to have residents taken outside as part of their daily activities.

While identifying limitations, certain potential confounding variables became evident and should be controlled for as much as possible during the project. The self-reported measures of depression could be influenced by the desire to please the project author. Because the project

author works with the patients in the facility, patients may want to appear less depressed to please the author. Also, the residents would be going outside with a staff member and this social interaction could lift the patient's depression thereby confounding social engagement with sunlight therapy. To address these measures a modification to the IRB will be sought to monitor other measures indicative of depression such as appetite, sleep patterns etc. as well as measures of social engagement as part of the intervention to address depression along with sunlight therapy.

Conclusion

This DNP project sought to implement sunlight therapy as an intervention to be utilized as adjunct therapy for OAs suffering from depression residing in a skilled nursing facility. This project is a programmatic evaluation approach and a review of literature incorporating sunlight therapy as a treatment modality. The utilization of sunlight therapy into practice would have been enhanced to help improve the lives of people suffering from depression. Due to the limitations, as discussed previously related to COVID-19 and facility support, this project had to be placed on hold. Older adults residing in nursing homes are demonstrably the group most at risk of adverse outcomes and mortality during this current pandemic (Fallon et al., 2020) Reducing symptoms of depression in this vulnerable population through evidence-based practice approach represents a significant opportunity to improve quality of life for these residents during and after this current crisis.

References

- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
- Baggerly, C. A., Cuomo, R. E., French, C. B., Garland, C. F., Gorham, E. D., Grant, W. B., & Wunsch, A. (2015). Sunlight and vitamin D: Necessary for public health. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 34(4), 359–365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.2015.1039866>
- Buckwalter, K., Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Kleiber, C., McCarthy, A., Rakel, B., Steelman, V., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Tucker, S. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews Evidence Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>
- Cameron, I. M., Crawford, J. R., Lawton, K., & Reid, I. C. (2008). Psychometric comparison of PHQ-9 and HADS for measuring depression severity in primary care. *British Journal General Practice*, 58(546), 32-36. <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp08X263794>
- Chang, C. H., Liu, C. Y., Chen, S. J., & Tsai, H. C. (2018). Efficacy of light therapy on nonseasonal depression among elderly adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 14, 3091–3102. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S180321>
- Charlesworth, C. J., Smit, E., Lee, D. S., Alramadhan, F., & Odden, M. C. (2015). Polypharmacy among adults aged 65 years and older in the United States: 1988–2010. *Journals of Gerontology Series A: Biomedical Sciences and Medical Sciences*, 70(8), 989-995. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glv013>

- Doody, C. M., & Doody, O. (2011). Introducing evidence into nursing practice: Using the Iowa model. *British Journal of Nursing*, 20(11), 661-664.
<https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2011.20.11.661>
- Durmaz, B., Soysal, P., Ellidokuz, H., & Isik, A. T. (2018). Validity and reliability of geriatric depression scale-15 (short form) in Turkish older adults. *Northern Clinics of Istanbul*, 5(3), 216-220. <https://doi.org/10.14744/nci.2017.85047>
- Durvasula, S., Sambrook, P., & Cameron, I. (2012). Factors influencing adherence with therapeutic sunlight exposure in older people in intermediate care facilities. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 54(2) 234-241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2011.08.009>
- Durvasula, S., Mason, R., Kok, C., Macara, M., Parmenter, T., & Cameron, I. (2015). Outdoor areas of Australian residential aged care facilities do not facilitate appropriate sun exposure. *Australian Health Review: A Publication of the Australian Hospital Association*, 39(4), 406-410. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AH14035>
- Fallon, A., Dukelow, T., Kennelly, S. P., & O'Neill, D. (2020). COVID-19 in nursing homes. *QJM : monthly journal of the Association of Physicians*, 113(6), 391–392.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcaa136>
- Frank, C. (2014). Pharmacologic treatment of depression in the elderly. *Canadian Family Physician*, 60(2), 121-126. Retrieved from
<https://www.cfp.ca/content/cfp/60/2/121.full.pdf>
- Gilbody, S., Richards, D., Brealey, S., & Hewitt, C. (2007). Screening for depression in medical settings with the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ): A diagnostic meta-analysis. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 22(11), 1596-1602.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-007-0333-y>

- Greenberg, P. E., Fournier, A., Sistsky, T., Pike, C., & Kessler, R. (2015). The economic burden of adults with major depressive disorder in the United States (2005 and 2010). *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 76, 2. <https://doi.org/10.4088/JCP.14m09298>
- Hamilton, M. (1960). A rating scale for depression. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery, and Psychiatry*, 23(1), 56–62. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp.23.1.56>
- Hanrahan, K., Fowler, C., & McCarthy, A. (2019). Iowa model revised: Research and evidence-based practice application. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 48, 121-122. <https://doi:10.1016/j.pedn.2019.04.023>
- Holick, M. F. (2011). Vitamin D: A d-lightful solution for health. *Journal of Investigative Medicine*, 59(6), 872–880. <https://doi.org/10.2310/JIM.0b013e318214ea2d>
- Kroenke, K., Spitzer, R. L., & Williams, J. B. (2001). The PHQ-9: Validity of a brief depression severity measure. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 16(9), 606–613. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1525-1497.2001.016009606>
- Kroenke, K., & Spitzer, R. L. (2002). The PHQ-9: A new depression diagnostic and severity measure. *Psychiatric Annals*, 32(9), 509-515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2016.03.030>
- Leggett, A. N., Conroy, D. A., Blow, F. C., & Kales, H. C. (2018). Bright Light as a Preventive Intervention for Depression in Late-Life: A Pilot Study on Feasibility, Acceptability, and Symptom Improvement. *The American journal of geriatric psychiatry: official journal of the American Association for Geriatric Psychiatry*, 26(5), 598–602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagp.2017.11.007>
- Lieverse, R., Van Someren, E., Nielen M., Uitdehaag, B., Smit, J., & Hoogendijk W. (2011) Bright light treatment in elderly patients with nonseasonal major depressive disorder: A

randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 68(1), 61–70.

<https://doi:10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2010.183>

Mitchell, A. J., Yadegarfar, M., Gill, J., & Stubbs, B. (2016). Case finding and screening clinical utility of the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9 and PHQ-2) for depression in primary care: A diagnostic meta-analysis of 40 studies. *Psychology Journal*, 2(2), 127-138.

<https://doi.org/10.1192/bjpo.bp.115.001685>

National Institutes of Health Office of Dietary Supplements. (2019). Vitamin D fact sheet for health professionals. <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/VitaminD-HealthProfessional/>

Oldham, M. A., & Ciraulo, D. A. (2014). Use of bright light therapy among psychiatrists in Massachusetts: An e-mail survey. *The Primary Care Companion for CNS Disorders*, 16(3). <https://doi:10.4088/PCC.14m01637>

Ortman, J. M., Velkoff, V. A., & Hogan, H. (2014). An aging nation: The older population in the United States. *United States Census Bureau*,

<https://www.census.gov/prod/2014pubs/p25-1140.pdf>

Parmelee, P., Lawton, M., & Katz, I. (1989.) Psychometric properties of the Geriatric Depression Scale among the institutionalized aged. *Psychology Assessment*, 1, 331–338.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/1040-3590.1.4.331>

Pedraza, O., Dotson, V., & Willis, F. (2009). Internal consistency and test-retest stability of the geriatric depression scale-short form in African American older adults.

Psychopathology Behavioral Assessment, 31, 412–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10862-008-9123-z>

Perera, S., Eisen, R., Bhatt, M., Bhatnagar, N., de Souza, R., Thabane, L., & Samaan, Z. (2016). Light therapy for non-seasonal depression: Systematic review and meta-

analysis. *Psychology Journal*, 2(2), 116–126.

<https://doi.org/10.1192/bjpo.bp.115.001610>

Polit, D.F., & Beck, C.T. (2017). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice*. Wolters Kluwer.

Ressler, K., & Nemeroff, C. (2000). Role of serotonergic and noradrenergic systems in the pathophysiology of depression and anxiety disorders. *Depression and Anxiety*, 1, 2-19.

<https://doi.10.1002/1520-6394200012:1>

Simning, A., & Simons, K. V. (2017). Treatment of depression in nursing home residents without significant cognitive impairment: A systematic review. *International Psychogeriatrics*, 29(2), 209–226. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610216001733>

Sumaya, I., Rienzi, B., Deegan, J., & Moss, D. (2001). Bright light treatment decreases depression in institutionalized older adults: A placebo-controlled crossover study. *The Journals of Gerontology*, 56(6), 356–360. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/56.6.M356>

Taylor, W. D. (2015). Should antidepressant medication be used in the elderly? *Expert Review of Neurotherapeutics*, 15(9), 961–963. <https://doi.org/10.1586/14737175.2015.1070671>

Varghese, F. P., & Brown, E. S. (2001). The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis in major depressive disorder: A brief primer for primary care physicians. *Primary Care Companion to the Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 3(4), 151–155.

<https://doi.org/10.4088/pcc.v03n0401>

Wancata, J, Alexandrowic, R., & Marquart, B. (2006). The criterion validity of the Geriatric Depression Scale: A systematic review. *Acta Psychiatrica Scand*, 114, 398–410.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0447.2006.00888>

- Weise, B. (2011). Geriatric depression: The use of antidepressants in the elderly. *British Columbia Medical Journal*, 53(47), 341-374. <https://www.bcmj.org/articles/geriatric-depression-use-antidepressants-elderly>
- Williams, J. B. (2001). Standardizing the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale: Past, present, and future. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*, 251(2), 6-12.
- Wittkamp, K. A., Naeije, L., Schene, A. H., Huyser, J., & van Weert, H. C. (2007). Diagnostic accuracy of the mood module of the patient health questionnaire: A systematic review. *General Hospital Psychiatry*, 29(5), 388-395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2016.03.030>
- Yesavage, J. A., Brink, T. L., Rose, T. L., Lum, O., Huang, V., Adey, M., & Leirer, V. O. (1982-3). Development and validation of a geriatric depression screening scale: A preliminary report. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 17(1), 37-49. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3956\(82\)90033-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3956(82)90033-4)
- Zhao, X., Ma, J., Wu, S., Chi, I., & Bai, Z. (2018). Light therapy for older patients with non-seasonal depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Affective Disorder*, 232, 291-299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2018.02.041>

Appendix A

Facility Agreement

Date : December 09, 2020

To : Cherie Harper
Administrator
Country Villa Plaza Nursing Center

From : Danielle Unrein, PMHNP – BC
[Redacted]

Re : Doctorate of Nursing Practice Project

This is an agreement between Country Villa Plaza Nursing Center and Danielle Unrein, PMHNP. This is authorizing Danielle Unrein to complete a pilot program at Country Villa Plaza Nursing Center. As previously described, this will be a 5-week study and residents will receive an informational cover letter. Danielle Unrein has taken the correct training to ensure all rights are protected of the residents residing at Country Villa Plaza Nursing Center.

Country Villa Plaza Nursing Center

Signature : [Redacted]

Print Name : Cherie Harper - Administrator

Danielle Unrein, PMHNP

Signature : [Redacted]

Print Name : Danielle Unrein, PMHNP-BC

Appendix B**Sunlight Therapy Flyer**

Sunlight Therapy Project

In this project, we hope to learn about sunlight therapy and how it affects symptoms of depression.

I will only ask you to participate in a five week project that will have you go outside for 30 minutes five days a week.

To participate you must be 50+ years old, currently being treated for depression, and not taking medication that causes photosensitivity.

To learn more, contact:

Elizabeth J. Winokur, PhD, RN, Principal Investigator

ewinok2@calstatela.edu

You can also contact:

Dani Unrein, MSN, RN, PMHNP, Co-Investigator
DNP Student, Cal State LA

dunrein@calstatefullerton.edu

If you would like to participate, please tell the Director of Nursing

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Appendix C

Informational Cover Letter

INFORMATIONAL COVER LETTER:

To Project Participant: Residents of skilled nursing facility.

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Danielle Unrein PMHNP-BC, BSN, RN, a graduate student at California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State, LA) and Elizabeth Winokur PhD, RN, an associate professor. In this study we hope to learn more about effects of sunlight on depression. You were selected to participate in this study because you meet all the inclusion criteria. We hope that our research will lead to decrease the symptoms of your depression and in hopes to create policies for the use of sunlight therapy in other nursing facilities. At any time, you can exclude yourself from this project and this intervention will not impede on any current therapies at the facility.

Before the start and at the end of the project you will complete a Patient Health Questionnaire-9 and Geriatric Screening Scale. You will be going outside with a facility staff for a time of 30 minutes after breakfast, while outside you are not required to do anything. This will take place five days out of the week. These days can be picked by you and at any time you can refuse to go outside. This will go on for five weeks and at the end you will do another Patient Health Questionnaire-9 and Geriatric Screening Scale.

There is minimal risk of loss of confidentiality. There is little risk and time in which this is taking place should be convenient and comfortable for you.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you choose to participate, we will protect your confidentiality. Residents will be de-identified using a random number that will be assigned to them in order to track their progress and completion of surveys for the project. De-identified data will be kept in a locked cabinet in the principal investigator's office at California State University of Los Angeles. This information will be kept for three years after completion of the project. As required by law if at any time you endorse suicidal ideations the Director of Nursing will be notified, and we will exclude you for the project.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Danielle Unrein at (818) 309-8264 or write her at daniunrein@csu.fullerton.edu 4952 Castana Ave, Lakewood CA 90712. Also you may call my team lead Dr. Elizabeth Winokur at (323)343-300 or write her at ewinokur2@exchange.calstatela.edu, 5151 State University Dr., Los Angeles, CA 90032

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Appendix D

GDS Short Form

Geriatric Depression Scale (short form)

Instructions: Circle the answer that best describes how you felt over the past week.

- | | | |
|---|-----|----|
| 1. Are you basically satisfied with your life? | yes | no |
| 2. Have you dropped many of your activities and interests? | yes | no |
| 3. Do you feel that your life is empty? | yes | no |
| 4. Do you often get bored? | yes | no |
| 5. Are you in good spirits most of the time? | yes | no |
| 6. Are you afraid that something bad is going to happen to you? | yes | no |
| 7. Do you feel happy most of the time? | yes | no |
| 8. Do you often feel helpless? | yes | no |
| 9. Do you prefer to stay at home, rather than going out and doing things? | yes | no |
| 10. Do you feel that you have more problems with memory than most? | yes | no |
| 11. Do you think it is wonderful to be alive now? | yes | no |
| 12. Do you feel worthless the way you are now? | yes | no |
| 13. Do you feel full of energy? | yes | no |
| 14. Do you feel that your situation is hopeless? | yes | no |
| 15. Do you think that most people are better off than you are? | yes | no |

Total Score _____

Appendix E

PHQ-9

PATIENT HEALTH QUESTIONNAIRE (PHQ-9)

ID #: _____ DATE: _____

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been
bothered by any of the following problems?
(use "✓" to indicate your answer)

	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	0	1	2	3
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	0	1	2	3
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	0	1	2	3
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	0	1	2	3
5. Poor appetite or overeating	0	1	2	3
6. Feeling bad about yourself—or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	0	1	2	3
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	0	1	2	3
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed. Or the opposite —being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	0	1	2	3
9. Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself	0	1	2	3

add columns + +

(Healthcare professional: For interpretation of TOTAL, TOTAL:
please refer to accompanying scoring card).

10. If you checked off any problems, how difficult have these problems made it for you to do your work, take care of things at home, or get along with other people?	Not difficult at all	_____
	Somewhat difficult	_____
	Very difficult	_____
	Extremely difficult	_____